

Paper 40**THE STUDY OF SOLAR CHARGE CONTROLLER
USING PWM TECHNIQUE AND A MODEL TO
IMPROVE ITS PERFORMANCE****P. Sridhar Acharya * P. S. Aithal ****

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E-mail: sridharaacharya@gmail.com* psaithal@gmail.com****Abstract**

The performance efficiency of solar energy is identified to be around 20%. The major portion of the solar energy produced will be lost due to several reasons like photon incident, impurities in the photovoltaic cell, the guiding media which is the copper wire offering resistance to the flow of current, the performance of the charge controller and the voltage level of the battery bank. Its really difficult to improve the efficiency of the solar energy due to the above reasons. The performance of solar charge controller is very essential to improve the efficiency of solar energy. The solar charge controller also plays a very important role in improving the life of the storage device. There are various types of solar charge controller available. Recently the solar energy system started using the PWM based charge controller technique to improve the performance of the solar energy system as well as to increase the life span of the battery backup. This paper contains the performance of solar charge controller using PWM technique. The variation in the charging depends on the pulse width. This paper proposes the new model in addition to the PWM charge controller to divert the solar energy to the load during short pulse width. This improves the performance efficiency of the solar energy.

1. Introduction

The most popular alternate renewable energy used in India is the solar energy. [1] This form of energy has a lot of advantages. The energy from solar PV panel is eco-friendly by contributing zero to the pollution [2] The Solar energy system is becoming more and more popular because this system can be used for a small power requirements to light a single bulb inside the small shop or street light to any power requirements for industries, commercial power requirements etc.[3] The installation of solar plants is easy and can be done in a bare land or roof top. The only requirement for the installation is the sufficient availability of sun light for a longer period in a day time. [4] The solar energy thus generated from the solar panel can be directly given to the load along with the available commercial electricity supply. [5]

In the same way the solar energy can be stored and then utilised using a hybrid technology. [6] Thus the solar energy can be considered as an alternate energy to the existing commercial energy system. This energy can be used along with the conventional commercial energy. This enables the consumer to go for any amount of power generation from the solar energy system.

The most challenging factor of the solar energy system is the efficiency of the same. [7] The total efficiency of the solar energy system is found to be 18% to 20%. There are various factors contributing to the low efficiency of the solar energy like[8]

- Performance of the photovoltaic cell due to impurities in the cell.
- Dust particle deposited on the surface of the solar panel.
- Incident of sunlight to the solar panel.
- Resistance offered by the conducting element which carries the solar energy to the storage device.
- Performance of the solar charge controller.

The major factor for the photovoltaic cell impurities is the minor charge carriers in the diode. [9]The improved technology using nano technology increases the efficiency by decreasing the impurities. But this increases the cost of the solar panel. [10] Due to the high production cost of the solar panel using nano technology, the panel is not affordable in the market.

Another factor which influences the efficiency of the solar panel is the deposition of the dust particles on the protective glass surface of the solar panel. The dust particle deposited on the glass surface will decrease the current in Amps when the sun light falls on the solar panel. [11] This reduces the efficiency of the solar energy system. This problem can be solved by regularly cleaning the panel.

One more factor which effects the performance of the solar energy is the varying incident of the sunlight throughout a day. [12] The maximum power output can be expected when the solar cell is placed perpendicular to the sunlight incident. [13] But in practice this is possible only for a few seconds. The variation in the sunlight incident changes the amount of current produced in Amps. For example if a panel is able to produce a current of say 7 Amps, the current of 7Amps can be produced only when the sun light is perpendicular to the solar panel. In reality the current varies from 0Amp to max 7 Amps and back to 0Amp in a day time from morning till evening.

The performance efficiency of the solar energy system is affected by the resistance offered by the conducting medium which carries the energy generated to the battery backup.[14] Normally the solar panels are mounted at the roof top where there is a sufficient amount of sunlight available. The solution to this loss is to minimise the distance between the solar panel and the battery backup. But the arrangement of the solar panel and battery backup depends on the building or geographical conditions.

The efficiency of the solar panel depends even on the charge controller which is used to charge a battery bank.[15] There are different technologies used for charging the battery bank in the solar energy system like transistor series and shunt switching circuit, PWM charge controller and MPPT based charge controller. The performance of these charge controllers differ from one another because of their performance characteristics. This results in the efficiency of the solar energy system.[16]

2. Objective

The objective of this paper is to study the performance of the solar charge controller using PWM technique and to propose a conceptual model which can improve the performance efficiency of the PWM solar charge controller.

3. Methodology

- The working principle of the PWM solar charge controller is explained.
- The conceptual model is introduced
- Working of the model
- The performance is analysed.

3.1 Working of PWM solar charge controller

The PWM solar charge controller uses a variable pulse generator. This variation in the pulse is due to the stored energy level in the battery bank. If the battery bank is having less energy stored then the pulse width will be more so that the energy from the solar panel can directly be stored in the battery backup. As the battery is getting charged the pulse width reduces and the charging rate also decreases. This technique improves the battery life. The conceptual diagram is shown in figure 1 and figure 2.

Figure 1. Performance of the PWM charge controller when battery backup is low

Figure 2. Performance of the PWM charge controller when battery backup is getting full

From the above two figures it is clear that when the battery backup is not full the solar energy is directly stored inside the battery backup. The charging pulse width goes on reducing when the battery backup is getting filled. This protects the battery backup from overcharging. Once the battery is fully charged the controller sends small pulse to sense the battery backup. If the battery is full then the charge controller will not charge the battery. Whereas if the battery backup needs charging then the pulse width will increase to charge the battery. To vary the pulse width the charge controller takes the battery voltage as a reference voltage.

The main drawback of this technology is the solar energy produced during the sunlight when the battery is fully charged. The charge controller will not charge the battery when the battery is full. During this period the solar energy produced will be wasted either in the form of heat or the panel may be damaged due to non-utilization of the solar energy.

3.2 The conceptual Model

The drawback of the PWM based solar charge controller is taken as an opportunity to develop a conceptual model. The idea behind the conceptual model is to divert the solar energy to the load when the battery is fully charged and divert to the battery backup when the charge in the battery is not full. The proposed model is shown in the figure 3.

Figure 3. The proposed New conceptual model.

3.3 Working of the model

The proposed model works like the regular PWM charge controller when the pulse width is more. This charges the battery at the rapid rate. When the battery is getting fully charged the pulse width decreases. This decrease in the pulse width reduces the charging rate. Once the battery is fully charged the pulse becomes a spike to sense the battery voltage.

The model has another load controller which sends the solar energy to the inverter. The inverter is connected to the load. The load controller gets the solar energy when the battery backup is either getting full or full. The input solar energy is given to the load though the inverter. The inverter is not just an ordinary inverter instead it is a smart inverter which will take the input energy from solar and in case required the additional energy is taken from the battery backup.

4. Analysis

The proposed model is utilising the solar energy to the maximum extent. Whenever the battery backup requires the energy to be stored the controller diverts the solar energy into the battery bank for charging whereas when the battery bank is getting full the solar energy is taken by the load controller which converts the energy into alternative energy and the load. Thus whatever energy produced by the solar PV system is utilised to the maximum extent.

5. Conclusion

The model is used efficiently by switching from charging mode to the connecting to the load mode. Whatever energy produced from the solar PV system is utilised to the maximum extent. This improves the overall efficiency of the model.

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